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GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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EVALUATION OF LAND USE LAND COVER CHANGES OF KIMBA/RITAWA GRAZING RESERVE IN NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This study focused on the evaluation of land use/land cover changes in Kimba/Ritawa grazing reserve in Northeastern Nigeria, using Remote Sensing Techniques. GIS Interpolation, Field inventory and observations were adopted to generate data for the study. The study revealed the trends in land classification and changes in the grazing reserve between the period of 2005 and 2020: the grass land which serves as the need for livestock feed drastically reduced due to encroachment with cultivated land and built-up areas rated at 73% in 2005, but slowly reduced in 2020 to 51%. This was attributed by the herders, to crop farming intensification and insurgency near the grazing reserve between 2005 and 2020. In conclusion, proper implementation of National Grazing Reserves Law for grazing land to be solely used for livestock grazing will go a long run in providing lasting solution to encroachment in to Kimba/Ritawa Grazing Reserve. The study recommended that there is need for enforcement of the Grazing Reserves Law of 1965 couple with proper monitoring and evaluation of the grazing reserve using modern GIS tools.*

Keywords: Land Use; Land Cover; Grazing Reserve; Northeastern Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Ecosystem degradation is commonly assessed based on vegetation conditions leading to different land types such as woodland, grassland, bareland and cultivated land (Teka *et al.* 2018 and Sato *et al.* 2019). Remote sensing technology and GIS provide efficient methods for analysis of vegetation cover issues and tool for land use planning (Cook & Pau, 2013). By understanding the driving force of landuse development in the past, managing current situation with modern GIS tools, for future use, one is able to develop plans for multiple uses of natural resources for conservation. Increasing human activities such as agriculture and settlement development have exerted so many tolls on the ecosystem of grazing reserves and has resulted in the loss of great proportion of vegetation (Teka *et al.* 2018 and Pfeiffer *et al.* 2019). Studies by Desta & Coppock (2004) have observed shift in crop land and livelihood activities in Borana grazing reserve.

Most grazing reserves and routes in Nigeria disappeared due to increasing settlements and cropping intensity. These are due to improper implementation of legal instrument to prevent encroachments (Ahmed *et al.* 2002). The traditional pattern of transhumance has been affected by high rate of degradation of pastureland due to over-stocking, poor nutrition, inadequate water supply, breed and breeding problems, poor diseases control and herd health management (Ducrotoy *et al.* 2018). To reduce the menace on these constraints in the traditional system, Nigerian Government came up with a National Grazing Reserves Law in 1965 (Shehu, 2018).

A close perusal of the National Grazing Reserves Law of 1965 reveals that it does not accommodate the present realities on ground. This has been attributed to the fact that fertile lands and land resources were in abundance at the time when such laws were made (Ogboru & Adejonwo-Osho, 2018). However, in reality

today is that land and land resources are faced with many challenges such as degradation, ecological changes and related socio-economic problems which are not considered by the law as at that time. The implication is that the law in its current state is inadequate in addressing contemporary issues relating to the sustainable management of grazing reserves in Northeast Nigeria.

Both natural and anthropogenic pressures are sources of continuous threat on grazing reserves in Nigeria and herders are among the people who are mostly affected (Chhabra *et al.* 2006 and Muhammad *et al.* 2019). Herders' approach over management of grazing lands consists of mobility of herds; strong community norms and regulations on pasture and water resource use (Angassa & Oba, 2008). Due to the fact that

there are increasing wave of encroachment into grazing reserves in Northeastern Nigeria, this study aimed to evaluate land use/ land cover changes of Kimba/Ritawa Grazing Reserve for the period of 15 years (2005-2020).

METHODOLOGY

STUDY AREA

The study area Kimba/Ritawa Grazing Reserve is found in Biu Local Government Area of Borno State, and covers an area of approximately 278 km². It is located between latitudes 10°42'32" to 10°55'30" N and longitudes 12°02'50" to 12°35'02" E. It shares boundaries with Damboa Local Government Area in the North, Shani Local Government Area in the South and East, and Sambisa Game Reserve in the West (Figure 1). The area is found mainly at Sudan Savanna region of Northeastern Nigeria.

Source: Environmental Management Department, BUK (2019).

Figure 1: Study Area

SPATIAL ANALYSIS

Three different data types were obtained for the classification of the grazing reserve. Landsat data were collected from United States

Geological Survey (USGS), an open-source repository of satellite images and their metadata were downloaded (Table 1). Eight Landsat imageries were collected for Kimba/Ritawa

Grazing Reserve. This was to cover for 2005, 2010, 2015 and 2020 respectively. A high resolution 0.3 meters pixel satellite images from google maps for the individual years were also obtained. Coordinates of the boundaries covering the grazing reserve were also obtained from Borno State Ministry of Land and Survey. The imageries were carefully selected for the study to avoid cloud covers or at most minimum cloud covers.

Table 1: Satellite Imageries Acquired for Four Different Times in Kimba/Ritawa Grazing Reserve

Month	Up & Down	2005		2010		2015		2020	
		Path	Row	Path	Row	Path	Row	Path	Row
March	Up	186	052	186	052	186	052	186	052
	Down	186	053	186	053	186	053	186	053

Source: Fieldwork (2020).

DATA PROCESSING

The 2005 and 2010 imageries were Landsat 7 imageries while the 2015 and 2020 imageries were Landsat 8 imageries. Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 were selected for Landsat 7 while band 8 was included for Landsat 8. The Landsat toolbox in ArcGIS was utilized to remove scan lines for all the bands in Landsat 7. All the 8 imageries were exported to a new dataset removing no data regions. They were further mosaic to have a complete cover of Kimba/Ritawa grazing reserve which happened to lie partly on two different image scenes (Up and Down). The composite band tool, an extension of ArcGIS data management tool was used to create composite bands. The google images for each year were georeferenced using the ArcGIS

georeferencing tool to ensure their exact position on the globe.

LAND COVER CLASSIFICATION

A folder was created and the composite band raster was inserted. The obtained coordinates for the grazing reserve were converted to a polygon using the point to polygon tool in ArcGIS. This is superimposed with the composite band raster and the google satellite images. The classification tool in ArcGIS was used to classify the various land covers. A supervised classification was used for this analysis to ensure better accuracy of the different land activities in the reserve. Grassland, forest, cultivated land, bare-ground and built-up areas were classified respectively (Table 2).

Table 2: Land cover Classes Used and their Brief Definition in Kimba/Ritawa

Number	Land Class	Brief Definition
1	Grassland	Area dominated by indigenous grasses and forbs
2	Forest	Area naturally covered by dense indigenous trees
3	Bare-ground	Area neither covered by vegetation nor used for crop production
4	Cultivated Land	Area used for cropping
5	Built-Up	Area used for settlement

Source: Teka *et al*, 2018

DATA ANALYSIS

Land classification and change detection was used for the analysis of 15 years satellite imagery of the grazing reserve. Descriptive statistics was carried out to obtained percentages of land cover changes from 2005-2020.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The result of the analyses of the trends in landuse and landcover changes (LULC) of Kimba/Ritawa grazing reserve at periods of 2005, 2010, 2015 and 2020 is presented in Table 3. The study revealed that there are five LU/LC classes; grassland, forest, cultivated land, bare-ground and built-up areas (Figure 2). Each of these classes was attributed to different changes between 2005 and 2020 (Table 4). In 2005 to 2010, encroachment due to cultivated land increases from 12% to 21%, built up decrease from 3% to 0%, Bare-ground increases from 5% to 6%. Grassland decreases from 73% to 62% and forest increase from 7% to 11% at the same period. This decrease in grassland was attributed to increase in encroachment due to crop farming activities in the area as reported by the herders in the grazing reserve.

Cultivated land decreased from 19% to 8% between 2015 to 2020, built up increased to 5% and further decreased to 0%, while Bare-ground

increased from 2% to 18%. Grassland decreased to 37% and increased to 51%, forest cover increased to 36% and decreased to 22% at the same period. Herders attributed these to insurgency in the region due to Boko Haram terrorist activities at that period, which made the herders to migrate to Ritawa village near Damboa town in Borno State. Kimba/Ritawa grazing reserve is neighbor to Southeastern part of Samba Game Reserve which is known to be terrorist area.

Oba and Kotile (2001) & Oba *et al.*, (2000) in their studies in Borana grazing reserve revealed persistent LULC changes and this might be related to different factors such as rainfall variability and heavy grazing pressure. Studies by Campbell *et al.* (2005) & Gemedo *et al.* (2006) observed increased cultivated and built-up in grazing reserve due to farming activities used as a substitute for lowering drought risk and rainfall uncertainty. These infiltration by large groups of farmers from the neighboring areas contributed to the expansion of cropping in the grazing land. Similar situation was observed in East African grazing reserve (Reid *et al.*, 2004). Chatty (2007) opined that, herdsman resist the expansion of cultivation and sedentarization, because it was going to reduces the size of their grazing reserve and mobility to utilize the distributed resources.

Table 3: Classification of LU/LC in Kimba/Ritawa Grazing Reserve

Land Type	2005		2010		2015		2020	
	km ²	%						
Grassland	203.1980	73	172.7366	62	104.2405	37	142.8769	51
Forest	20.5501	7	31.6203	11	101.1790	36	60.2145	22
Bareground	13.2841	5	15.4751	6	5.1817	2	51.0253	18
Cultivation	32.4579	12	57.3521	21	53.9834	19	22.9226	8
Built up	8.5111	3	0.8171	0	13.4165	5	0.9618	0
Total	278.0012	100	278.0012	100	278.0012	100	278.0012	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2021

Table 4: Herder’s Perceived Attribute towards Grassland Cover Changes in the Study Area

Major Driving Forces	Respondents (%)	
	2005-2010	2015-2020
Crop Farming	57.32	38.12
Insurgency (Boko Haram)	14.41	55.34
Settlement	18.10	5.81
Rainfall Variability	8.01	0.73
Over Stocking	2.16	0
Total	100	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2021

(N=506)

Figure 2: Extracted and Classified Satellite Imagery of Kimba/Ritawa Grazing Reserve
Source: Fieldwork, 2021.

CONCLUSION

A close perusal of the findings from land classification and change from 2005 to 2020, Kimba/Ritawa Grazing Reserve was subjected to encroachment due to cultivated land and insurgency due to Boko Haram terrorist activities. The expansions of cultivated land and insurgency in Kimba/Ritawa grazing reserve of

northeastern Nigeria have affected fodder production for livestock. Voluntary cultivation has been established in the grazing reserve for generating income for livelihood support. Hence, these reduced the size of the grazing reserve and mobility of livestock to utilize the unevenly distributed resources in the environment. Thus, if this situation continues, it results in destruction of important fodder crop,

land degradation and soil infertility. it is recommended that, there is need for enforcement on the law providing and managing grazing reserve in the region, because grazing reserve is a protected area solely created for livestock grazing but currently encroached with

crop farming and built-up settlements. These lead to degradation of important fodder crops and render the land overgrazed. Government at all level has the enforcement measures with the use of its grazing reserve rangers to control encroachment in to Kimba/Ritawa grazing reserve.

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